

Prevalence of *Acinetobacter* Infection in Hospital Environment and their Antimicrobial Sensitivity Pattern in North-East Region of Bangladesh

Mohammad Abul Hasnat¹, Md.Waseque Mia¹, Zafrul Hasan¹, Sharmin Sultana Panna²

¹Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, Shahjalal University of Science and Technology, Sylhet-3114, Bangladesh

²Food and Nutrition Science, Ibn Sina Hospital Sylhet Limited, Sylhet, Bangladesh

Abstract— *Acinetobacter* species are the most important nosocomial and opportunistic pathogens. In South-Asian countries including Bangladesh, prevalence of *Acinetobacter* infection in hospital environment and their resistance to antimicrobial agents is significantly high. In this study, the prevalence of *Acinetobacter* infection from various hospitals and its correlation with patient's age, sex, hospital units, and different season were evaluated. In addition, the sensitivity patterns of *Acinetobacter* to different 23 antimicrobial agents were also assessed. Comparatively higher infection rate by *Acinetobacter* species was found in patients with lung infection, urinary tract infection and abscess. Interestingly, significantly higher infection by *Acinetobacter* was also seen at rainy season in intensive care unit (ICU), and medicine unit. Remarkably, antibiotic colistin was found with highest susceptibility (96.4%) followed by tigecycline (89.6%), imipenem (57.7%) and meropenem (51.4%). Rest of the 19 antibiotics showed less than 50% susceptibility. Therefore, this hospital based study on *Acinetobacter* infection suggesting to implement a strict antibiotic management policy of its spread among the patients.

Keywords— *Acinetobacter*; prevalence; hospital environment; season; susceptibility.

I. INTRODUCTION

Acinetobacter are Gram-negative *Coccobacilli* bacteria and strictly aerobic, catalase positive, non-motile, oxidase negative and lack pigmentation [1]. They are free living saprophytes in soil and water [2-3]. As opportunistic pathogen, *Acinetobacter* have a high incidence among immunocompromised individuals, particularly those who have experienced a prolonged hospital stay [4]. *Acinetobacter* commonly associated with aquatic environments [5], they have been shown to colonize the skin as well as being isolated in high numbers from the respiratory and urinary tract secretions of infected individuals [6].

They are reported to cause a number of outbreaks of nosocomial infections such as septicemia, pneumonia, wound sepsis, endocarditis, meningitis, urinary tract infections and peritonitis [7], but their predominant role is in ventilator associated pneumonia (VAP), in intensive care units (ICUs) [1]. Risk factors for multidrug-resistant *Acinetobacter* colonization and infection include prolonged length of hospital stay, exposure to the intensive care unit (ICU), mechanical ventilation, central venous catheterization, urinary catheterization, prior exposure to antimicrobials, greater severity of illness, surgery, and receipt of invasive procedures [8, 9, 10].

The prevalence of *Acinetobacter* infection is variable depending on the geographical localization and the patient's socio-economic status [11-13], in an international study in ICUs, the *Acinetobacter* infections rate was 19.2% in Asia; 17.1% in Eastern Europe; 14.8% in Africa; 13.8% in Central and South America; 5.6% in Western Europe; 4.4% in Oceania and 3.7% in North America [13]. It is 15% in South African HIV-positive patients [11] and 13% in Canadian burn

care units [12]. In our region, no study on *Acinetobacter* prevalence has been performed.

In recent years, *Acinetobacter* have been designated as a “red alert” human pathogen, generating alarm among the medical fraternity, arising largely from its extensive antibiotic resistance spectrum [14]. *Acinetobacter* are opportunistic pathogen known for its intrinsic resistance to antibiotics and greater ability to rapidly acquire resistance genes as mobile genetic elements (plasmids, transposons, integrons cassettes and insertion sequences) [15-17]. Multidrug resistant (MDR) *Acinetobacter* are becoming a global threat with a therapeutic impasse increasingly described in literature [18-20]. Indeed this organism generally has resistance to several antibiotics. According to the literature data, the resistance rate varies from 31.8 to 92.1% to ceftazidime; 8.8 to 89.9% vs imipenem, from 12.2 to 89.9% vs. Piperacillin / Tazobactam, from 28.8 to 91.6% vs. fluoroquinolones and 30 to 90.3% vs. aminoglycosides [11, 21-24] but colistin is often the only effective treatment option whereas some *Acinetobacter* strains develop resistance to colistin [11, 22-25]. Resistance to colistin was estimated to 5.3% in the United States [25]; 2.7% in South Africa [11]; 1.2% in India [24] and 0.9% in Tunisia [23] and 0.5% in Saudi Arabia [22].

In north-east area (Sylhet) of Bangladesh, no study on prevalence of *Acinetobacter* infection and their antibiotic susceptibility have been performed. This study was conducted to determine the frequency of *Acinetobacter* infection in hospitalized patients and observed their antimicrobial susceptibility pattern.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Population and Sample Collection

The study was carried out in the Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology of Shahjalal University of science and Technology, Sylhet, Bangladesh, from August, 2016 to July, 2018. Relevant diagnostic specimens like sputum, tracheal aspirate, urine, pus and wound swab etc. were collected from different units of MAG Osmani Medical College and Hospital, North-east Medical college and Hospital and Nurjahan Hospital Ltd, Sylhet, Bangladesh by standard collection procedures including infection type, season of infection, patient's name, sex and age. Few Technical supports were taken from a well known Diagnostic Centre named Medinova Medical Services Ltd. Sylhet, Bangladesh. About 113 *Acinetobacter* positive samples were collected and observed to complete this study. Specimens were processed by standard microbiological techniques [26].

Bacterial Identification and Sensitivity Pattern Test

Primary culture of *Acinetobacter* was performed on MacConkey agar medium at 37°C for 24 hours [3]. Pure culture and the study of antibiotic susceptibility were performed by the disc diffusion method on Mueller-Hinton agar plates. Gram stains, Indole test, Kigler Iron Agar (KIA), Simon Citrate Agar test, Catalase, Oxidase and Motility tests were also performed to identify *Acinetobacter*.

The antibiotic discs tested were cephradine, amoxicillin, cefuroxime, cefixime, cefotaxime, nalidexic acid, amoxiclav, ceftriaxone, ticarcillin, mecillinum, ciprofloxacin, nitrofurantoin, levofloxacin, ceftazidime, cotrimoxazole, gentamicin, amikacin, doripenem, piperacillin, meropenem, imipenem, tigecycline and colistin.

Graphical Analysis

Pie chart and bar diagrams were produced by using data obtained from questionnaire and sensitivity pattern tests. Pie chart was produced for each infection type caused by *Acinetobacter* and bar diagrams were produced for prevalence of *Acinetobacter* at different hospital units at different seasons of the year and also for sensitivity and resistance pattern of *Acinetobacter* to different antimicrobial agents.

III. RESULTS

During the study period of August, 2016 to July, 2018, 113 *Acinetobacter* positive sample were collected from different indoor unit (ward) like Intensive Care Unit (ICU), Medicine, Gynae, Surgery, Orthopedics and Nephrology wards of MAG Osmani Medical college and hospital, North-east Medical College and Hospital and Nurjahan Hospital Pvt. Limited, Sylhet (north-east region), Bangladesh.

Sputum, tracheal aspirate, urine, pus, blood and wound swab were collected as specimen and among that 113 *Acinetobacter* positive sample, 65 (57.5%) and 48 (42.5%) were male and female respectively.

According to this study, among all 113 samples, 48 (42.5%), 22 (19.5%), 21 (18.5%), 16 (14.2%) and 6 (5.3%) were suffered from lung infection, urinary tract infection, abscess, wound infection and septicemia respectively.

Among the collected 113 *Acinetobacter* positive patient's sample, 100 were infected after admitted in hospital. Science the samples were collected from different units of hospitals so a comparative study of prevalence of *Acinetobacter* infection among the hospital units was done. Among that 100 *Acinetobacter* positive sample, 40 (40%), 32 (32%), 14 (14%), 8(8%), 4 (4%) and 2 (2%) samples were collected from Intensive Care Unit (ICU), Medicine, Gynae, Surgery, Orthopedics and Nephrology units respectively.

Infection rate of *Acinetobacter* at various seasons of the year was the finding of the study. Prevalence of *Acinetobacter* infection in hospitalized patients at different seasons also a finding of this study. About 42.9%, 35.7% and 21.4% patient were infected at rainy, winter and summer season respectively.

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